

Results and Discussion

A solid state interaction occurs when varying amounts of urea oxalate and a fixed amount (1 g mole) of ferric or aluminium phosphate are ground together in the powdery form for 1 to 2 hr. The resulting product becomes completely water soluble when the mole ratio of the iron phosphate to urea oxalate is 1 : 1 because of the formation of soluble monoferric phosphate and ferric oxalate. In the case of aluminium system the resulting product becomes cent per cent water soluble only at the stage of 1 : 2 mole ratio, because of the conversion of sparingly soluble aluminium oxalate formed at the stage of 1 : 1 mole ratio into soluble complex oxalate compound. The complex formation is supported by the fact that at the stage of 1 : 2 mole ratio iron or aluminium could be not detected in the resulting product by ionizable reactions.

The nature of curves (Fig. 1) obtained on plotting the fraction of water soluble and citrate soluble P_2O_5 against varying amounts of ferric phosphate or aluminium phosphate and urea oxalate mixture clearly shows the experimental results.

Fig. 1.

It seems that the reaction between urea oxalate and iron or aluminium phosphate takes place due to the mobility of hydrogen and oxalate ions. At the points of contact of the two solids, protonation of the phosphate ions occurs as a result of the movement of labile H^+ ions from urea oxalate. Grinding increases the activation energy of the reaction and has a marked effect on the course of a solid state interaction. On grinding the textural and structural states of solids change and fresh surfaces of the reactants are exposed which enhances the rate of the

chemical reaction. To confirm that the reaction takes place in the solid state, physical methods like infra red spectrum and X-ray powder diffraction are adopted, where the solvent does not play any role at all. The work is being continued in this direction.

Thus it can be concluded that acid soils which invariably contain ferric and/or aluminium phosphate may be made available to plants in presence of excess of urea oxalate.

References

1. S. N. CHAKRAVARTI, Ph.D. Thesis, London University, 1959.
2. T. R. N. KUTTY and A. R. V. MURTHY, *Indian J. Technol.*, 1972, 10, 408.
3. G. N. PANT and D. N. PATEAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 101.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text-Book of Practical Organic Chemistry Including Qualitative Organic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co., London, 3rd ed., 1961.
5. OFFICIAL METHODS OF ANALYSIS: Association of Official Agricultural Chemists, Washington, 1960, p. 9.

Synthesis of analogues of Glycozolidine

P. BHATTACHARYYA, S. P. BASAK,
A. ISLAM & D. P. CHAKRABORTY
Bose Institute, Calcutta 700 009

Manuscript received 13 December 1975; revised 10 May 1976;
accepted 10 May 1976

GLYCOZOLIDINE¹, $C_{15}H_{15}NO_2$, m.p. $161^{\circ}-62^{\circ}$, the second carbazole alkaloid isolated from the root bark of *Glycosmis pentaphylla* (Retz.) D.C., was shown to be a 3-methyl carbazole derivative with two methoxyl groups. One of the methoxyls was at 2 or 7 position. In consideration of the N.M.R. data of the compound 5 : 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl carbazole formulation (I) of glycozolidine was considered consistent². Recently it has been shown that some of the carbazole alkaloids or its congeners had antibiotic activity. In order to confirm the structure of glycozolidine and to test the antibiotic action of the carbazole derivatives, synthesis of 6 : 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl (II) and 5 : 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl (I) carbazole was undertaken. The present communication reports synthesis of these compounds, which were different from glycozolidine. Recently the structure of glycozolidine has been settled as 2 : 6-dimethoxy-3-methyl carbazole(III) ^{3a, 3b, 3c, 4}.

In the synthesis of these two carbazoles, we followed the method and procedure previously adopted in our laboratory⁶. The appropriate dimethoxy aniline derivative (V) were reacted with 2-hydroxymethylene-5-methyl cyclohexanone (IV) to yield the corresponding substituted hydrazones (VI). The hydrazones on indolisation with glacial acetic acid and hydrochloric acid furnished the appropriate 3-methyl-1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (VII). On reduction of the oxo compound by Wolff-Kishner method

(A) 5-7-DIMETHOXY-3-METHYL CARBAZOLE AND ITS PRECURSORS;

(B) 6:7-DIMETHOXY-3-METHYL CARBAZOLE AND ITS PRECURSORS;

TABLE I

Hydroxymethylene	Starting amines	Properties of hydrazone	Properties of oxo tetra hydrocarbazole	Properties of tetra hydrocarbazole	Properties of carbazole
2-Hydroxymethylene 5-methylcyclohexanone.	3,5-dimethoxyaniline	V(A) red crystals, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, m.p. $115^\circ\text{--}117^\circ$	VI(A) white crystals, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$, m.p. $120^\circ\text{--}22^\circ$	VII(A) Tarry product	I, crystalline compound, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$, m.p. $163^\circ\text{--}64^\circ$. $\lambda_{\text{ethanol}}^{\text{max}}$ 233, 237, 280, 309 nm $\log \epsilon$ 4.47, 4.47, 4.08, 4.20 $\nu_{\text{Nujol}}^{\text{max}}$ 3410, 1615, 1500, 1410, 1208 cm^{-1}
2-Hydroxymethylene 5-methyl cyclohexanone.	4-Amino veratrole	V(B) red crystals, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, m.p. 95° .	VI(B) colourless crystalline solid m.p. 110°	VII(B) oily product	II, crystalline compound, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$, m.p. 185° . $\lambda_{\text{ethanol}}^{\text{max}}$ 236, 265, 303 nm $\log \epsilon$ 4.66, 4.18, 4.32 $\nu_{\text{Nujol}}^{\text{max}}$ 3420, 1620, 1500, 1470, 1400 cm^{-1}

Since this work was complete, our conclusion has been supported by photolytic synthesis of some dimethoxy-3-methyl carbazole derivative by Weinstein and Das⁶.

the appropriate tetrahydrocarbazole (VIII) was obtained. These on dehydrogenation with 10% Pd-C in alcohol furnished the desired carbazoles. The reaction is schematically represented as follows and the properties of the reaction products are detailed in the Table 1.

References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. P. DAS, *Science and Culture*, 1966, 32, 181.
2. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. P. DAS, K. C. DAS and B. C. DAS, Proc. IUPAC Symp. on Natural Products, 1966, p. 182.
- 3(a) D. P. CHAKRABORTY, A. ISLAM and P. BHATTACHARYYA, Proc. IUPAC Symp. on the Chemistry of Natural Products, 1972, p. 2.
- (b) A. ISLAM, P. BHATTACHARYYA and D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Comm.*, 1972, 537.
- (c) D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. P. DAS and S. P. BASAK, *Plant Biochem. J.*, 1974, 11, 73.
4. (Mrs.) F. ANWER, R. S. KAPIL and S. P. POPLI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 959.
5. K. C. DAS and BORIS WEINSTEIN, *J. Medicine Chem.*, 1972, 14, 1021.
6. D. P. CHAKRABORTY and B. K. CHOWDHURY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 33, 1265.

Potentiometric Study of the Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with Schiff Base Derived from Sulphaphenazole and Salicylaldehyde

PRABUDDHA JAIN & KAMAL K. CHATURVEDI

Department of Chemistry, Holkar Science College, Indore

Manuscript received 10 February 1976; revised 10 May 1976; accepted 7 June 1976

CONDENSATION products of sulphonamides with salicylaldehyde have been found to be good bacteriostatic^{1,2} as well as good complexing agents³⁻⁶. Therefore it was decided to synthesise sulphaphenazole salicylaldehyde (SPHSA) and to study complex formation of SPHSA with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) potentiometrically.

Experimental

All chemicals employed were of Analar grade. Metal perchlorates were prepared and analysed as reported earlier⁴. SPHSA was prepared by the method described earlier⁴.

The Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique^{7,8} as used by Irving and Rossotti⁹ has been applied to determine protonation constant of the ligand and formation constants of complexes.

The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration against sodium hydroxide (CO₂ free) of the three mixtures. Set 1. Perchloric acid; Set 2. Perchloric acid+SPHSA Set 3. Perchloric acid+SPHSA+Metal solution.

Such that the concentration of the common ingredients were identical in different solutions, neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added so as to maintain ionic strength 0.2M. A pH meter (Beckmann model H2) was used for pH measurement.

To calculate the formation constant of the ligand proton system and values of n_A at different pH values were calculated using Set 1 and Set 2 titration curves. The ligand protonation formation curve was obtained by plotting the graph between n_A values and pH. $\bar{n}$ values were calculated using Set 2 and Set 3 titration curves. The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pL.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves it is observed that metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curves which proves that the liberation of protons is due to chelation. Least square method was applied to determine the metal-ligand stability constants. The values at an ionic strength ($\mu=0.2M$) have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Ion	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log β	Log K_1/K_2	ΔG Kcal/mole	σ
H	Log $\beta^H = 6.2$					
Cu(II)	5.64	3.24	8.88	2.40	-12.13	± 0.0005
Ni(II)	5.20	2.68	7.88	2.52	-10.75	± 0.0013
Co(II)	4.60	1.82	6.42	2.78	- 8.77	± 0.0110

The result reveals that condensation products Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) form complexes with SPHSA and the sequence of stability is Cu>Ni>Co which is in accordance with Irving and Williams¹⁰.

The large difference between successive stability constants may be attributed to the greater steric hindrance offered by SPHSA than coordinated water molecules.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a research fellowship to P.J.

References

1. TAKEO TSUKAMATO and KENOSUKE YUHI, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1958, 78, 706; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 52, 14561b.
2. TAKEO TSUKAMATO, Takeda Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd., Japan, 1960, 5766; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 55, 5879f.
3. R. R. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 385.
4. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 805.
5. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* 1976, 38, 799.
6. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1220, 1225.
7. J. BJERRUM, 'Metalamine Formation in Aqueous Solution', Haese, Copenhagen.
8. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
9. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAM, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 749.